

Solid Waste Management System of Kushtia Municipality

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Abstract

The increasing quantity of solid waste is a growing environmental problem in Bangladesh. Solid Waste Management is considered as one of the most serious problems in developing countries like Bangladesh. Unplanned and inadequate collection of solid wastes contributes greatly to an unhealthy environment. Urbanization is increasing day by day in this country and Kushtia is one of the busiest cities among them. The people of Kushtia City generate large quantities of waste. So, Waste management is one of the most serious problems of Kushtia Municipality. This research paper explores the problems and prospects of waste management in Kushtia Municipality.

Keywords: Solid Waste, Waste Generation and collection, Recycling, Environmental issue, Final disposal, Landfill

Introduction

Solid waste means useless, unwanted, and discarded materials coming from production and consumption. Many of these items can be considered waste such as domestic rubbish, sewage sludge, wastes from manufacturing activities, packaging items, discarded cars, discarded electronic devices, garden waste, old paint containers, etc. All human daily activities can give rise to a large variety of different wastes arising from different sources. Based on the sources, solid waste can be classified into various kinds which include Municipal Solid Waste, Industrial Waste, Agricultural Waste, and hazardous waste. The characteristics of waste are heterogenous and may vary seasonally. Unorganized management of solid waste is a noticeable problem of the ruin of the environment in most cities. Kushtia Municipal Corporation is trying to manage this problem but they are unable to control waste management. On the other hand, solid waste management has so far been the most ignored and least studied area in environmental sanitation in most developing countries, but recently the concerned agencies have begun to consider this area to be an inseparable component of improved public health. In 2022-2023, the population of the city of Kushtia, Bangladesh is 108423 people and the people of this city generate a large amount of solid waste which needs to be managed properly due to reduce environmental pollution. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the advantages and disadvantages of the solid waste management system in the Kushtia Municipality. The sources of solid wastages are garbage, refuse, and discarded material and the wastages are produced by industry, hospital, or household

community activities. Waste management is a tactic used to waste collection largely from different sources, including recycling and re-use of materials.

Impact of Solid Waste Disposal On the Environment

- Foul odor near waste storage bins that are not emptied regularly or not washed and disinfected (M. Feroze Ahmed, June, 2000)
- Open-air dumping creates unhygienic and poses an enormous threat to the people (Islam, 2016)
- Blocking of drainage systems resulting in wastewater overflow due to indiscriminate dumping of solid wastes
- Promotes the spreading of diseases
- Land pollution from untreated and inadequately treated industrial wastes containing toxic substances and heavy metals (Islam, 2016)
- Carbon dioxide and Methane produced from solid waste are extremely harmful to the environment (Islam, 2016)
- Gases are produced in landfills through aerobic and anaerobic decomposition of organic compounds, which are a threat to the environment.

Study Area

The study area was Kushtia City. It's one of the largest cities in Bangladesh.

Study Duration

17 April 2023 to 29 April 2023

Objectives

- To discuss about the sources of solid waste and its composition
- To discuss the applicability of waste management systems in terms of disposal collection and temporary storage, reuse, recycling, and treatment
- To discuss public participation in recycling, employment, and financial benefit

Solid waste management in Kushtia City

Waste Generation:

It involves those activities in which materials are identified as no longer being of value and therefore, are thrown away as useless or gathered together for disposal. (Howard S. Peavy, 1985)

In this city, wastes are generated in different types of human activities. The wastes are usually municipal waste, industrial waste, and hazardous waste there is very little amount of agricultural waste.

Functional Element of Solid Waste Management System

On-Site Handling and Storage

This is an important element in the overall solid waste management system because it can have significant effects on public health and on subsequent functional elements of the system. On-site handling refers to the activities associated with the handling of solid wastes until they are placed

Fig-1: Storage of solid waste

in a container for storage and collection. This activity includes manual sorting in Kushtia municipality.

Nature of waste composition in Kushtia

- Food and vegetable waste
- Plastics
- Wood
- Glass and ceramics
- Paper products
- Metals
- Garden waste
- Other (Stone dirt etc.)

Collection of Solid Wastes

The collection of solid wastes in the Kushtia municipality area is becoming a difficult and complex task. The primary reason is that the generation of solid waste is a diffuse process that occurs in a variety of places including individual homes, multi-stored apartment buildings, commercial and industrial facilities, as well as streets, parks, and even the vacant areas of every community. There are several methods for the collection of solid waste

- Communal collection
- Block collection
- Curb-side collection
- House to house to collection

In Kushita municipality House to house collection system is used. Local collectors use simple manually driven rickshaw vans (Fig-3) for house-to-to waste collection. Apart from some minor difficulties, the approach appears to be working satisfactorily. Households participating in this initiative are paying 125TK per month collected by the local organizers to meet the operation and maintenance costs.

Fig-2: Solid waste in roadside

Fig-3: Gathering waste in transfer station

Transportation

A small van is used to collect the waste and used to haul the waste to the transfer station and a large vehicle (tilt-type truck) is used for hauling the waste to the final disposal site. And all are non-compaction vehicles.

Processing

The main purpose of the processing of solid wastes are

- To improve the efficiency of solid waste management systems
- To recover useable material
- To recover conversion products and energy

In this city, several important techniques are used

- Mechanical volume reduction – Compacton
- Chemical volume reduction- Not used
- Component separation- manual sorting method is used
- Mechanical size reduction – Shredding
- Moisture content reduction – drying and dewatering

Most of these techniques used primarily to improve the efficiency of overall solid waste management systems.

Recycling process in Kushtia

Recycling and reclamation are now strongly promoted for the conservation of resources and preventing and prevention of environmental degradation. In Kushtia, wastes having some market value are being reclaimed in three stages. In the first stage, housewives separate refuse of higher market value such as papers, bottles, fresh containers old clothes, shoes, etc, and sell them to street hawkers.

Mostly children of slum dwellers known as 'Tokai' carry out the second stage of salvaging. They collect different items of low market value from waste collection bins. The items include broken glass, cans, cardboard, waste papers, rags, plastics, metals, and miscellaneous commercial wastes discarded by households. Scavengers at the final disposal sites do the third stage of salvaging when municipal trucks unload refuse.

and drains are not good. 70% of cleaners accumulate the waste from roadsides from the roadside and transfer it to the nearest dustbin/container often, and 30% do these activities daily. So, in this case, Kushtia Municipality cleaner's activities are not good enough. Waste collection is not efficiently planned and does not reach all communities in most places, the municipality is collecting waste only once a week, a practice that has created illegal dumping. So, it is clear that there is a big problem with regularity in the Kushtia Municipality waste management system.

Conclusion

In Bangladesh, we have some common dreams that are a neat, clean, and poverty-free society, and the waste recycling process can help to bring these dreams into reality. But government alone cannot bear the responsibility. We have to work together and share these responsibilities. The above study reveals clearly that Kushtia Municipality has a successful history of the waste management system and doing better day by day. At present, the municipality is working in this sector in full swing. But there are some challenges and opportunities. If the government and non-government organizations assist and the municipal authority is careful about this, the inhabitants of Kushtia City will get a better, environmentally safe, and pollution-free Kushtia.

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